
Corona data analysis tool

A Data Management Plan created using DMPonline

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Project abstract:

In this project we have implemented a tool for calculating statistical data for a corona virus data set. Several statistics, e.g. top ten countries with most cases worldwide are calculated and displayed visually in interactive plots.

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Corona data analysis tool - Final review DMP

1. Data summary

State the purpose of the data collection/generation

The data is collected to keep track of the COIV-19 pandemic numbers and statistics world wide in order to e.g. estimate the severity and to be able to react accordingly.

Explain the relation to the objectives of the project

The goal of the project is to calculate statistics and visualize them in a user friendly way s.t. it is easy to get an overview of the data, in this case of the numbers of the disease.

Specify the types and formats of data generated/collected

The data used is raw data in a csv file, that includes dates, numbers and strings. The data generated is mainly data in a raw output format

Specify if existing data is being re-used (if any)

The inital data set as provided by the european union is being used as input.

Specify the origin of the data

The input data was downloaded from the open data website of the european union (corona virus data)

State the expected size of the data (if known)

The input dataset is 365,1 KB large.

Outline the data utility: to whom will it be useful

The statistical numbers the tool calculates are useful for everybody who wants to get a quick overview of the current worldwide situation of the corona virus data.

2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata [FAIR data]

Outline the discoverability of data (metadata provision)

The input data is openly accessible on the website of the European Union and also referenced by via a DOI: European Centre For Disease Prevention And Control (2020) ‘Sonraí faoi choróinvíreas COVID-19’. Publications Office. doi: 10.2906/101099100099/1. The Data as well as the experiment code (the whole experiment) is published via the public Github repository with the DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3749725 or the Zenodo link: <https://zenodo.org/badge/latestdoi/250611063> or the direct Github link: <https://github.com/lucasberent/ds/tree/v1.0.0>.

The DOI for this DMP is: 10.5281/zenodo.3749735

Outline the identifiability of data and refer to standard identification mechanism. Do you make use of persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers?

The raw input data used is made public in a public github repository which is identified by a doi, also this DMP is identified by a DOI. The provider of the original dataset, the EU has also created a reference for the dataset via doi: 10.2906/101099100099/1.

Outline naming conventions used

No special naming conventions were used.

Outline the approach towards search keyword

There is no approach towards search keywords made, except for the DOI and the information in the README included in the public repository.

Outline the approach for clear versioning

Versioning is done through the github repository.

Specify standards for metadata creation (if any). If there are no standards in your discipline describe what metadata will be created and how

There are no real standards by the means of this experiment. The most important metadata is information disclosed in this DMP, author name, information disclosed via the Github repository.

2.2 Making data openly accessible [FAIR data]

Specify which data will be made openly available? If some data is kept closed provide rationale for doing so

All data, i.e. input data, the implementation of the experiment and the output will be made available publicly.

Specify how the data will be made available

The data and experiment implementation is uploaded on a public github repository.

Specify what methods or software tools are needed to access the data? Is documentation about the software needed to access the data included? Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

The experiment needs to be built with maven and executed with java as a jar file. The relevant built and run information is disclosed directly in a readme in the public repository.

Specify where the data and associated metadata, documentation and code are deposited

The whole experiment is uploaded to a public github repository.

Specify how access will be provided in case there are any restrictions

There are no restrictions.

2.3 Making data interoperable [FAIR data]

Assess the interoperability of your data. Specify what data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies you will follow to facilitate interoperability.

The experiment is implemented in java and csv formats are used for technical interoperability.

Specify whether you will be using standard vocabulary for all data types present in your data set, to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability? If not, will you provide mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

All datatypes used are standard data types, as strings, integers and dates.

2.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licenses) [FAIR data]

Specify how the data will be licenced to permit the widest reuse possible

Because of the MIT license the data can be reused from the github repository there are no restrictions.

Specify when the data will be made available for re-use. If applicable, specify why and for what period a data embargo is needed

There are no a priori restrictions to data reuse.

Specify whether the data produced and/or used in the project is useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project? If the re-use of some data is restricted, explain why

Because of the MIT license the data can be reused from the github repository there are no restrictions.

Describe data quality assurance processes

There is no professional quality assurance process implemented. The integrity of the input dataset is provided by the EU open data initiative.

Specify the length of time for which the data will remain re-usable

There are no apriori restrictions to data reuse.

3. Allocation of resources

Estimate the costs for making your data FAIR. Describe how you intend to cover these costs

The only costs that would arise are costs of hosting the public repository but since this is an educational project there are none.

Clearly identify responsibilities for data management in your project

Since this is a one man project all responsibilities are incorporated in one person which is also the author an holder of this DMP.

Describe costs and potential value of long term preservation

There are no costs, except maybe for repository hosting.

4. Data security

Address data recovery as well as secure storage and transfer of sensitive data

No sensitive data is used or produced.

5. Ethical aspects

To be covered in the context of the ethics review, ethics section of DoA and ethics deliverables. Include references and related technical aspects if not covered by the former

None

6. Other

Refer to other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management that you are using (if any)

None